

With Fond Memories of Ron Probst, Tom Kinman, and Roger Lynds

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NSF's NOIRLab lost three giants in the past six months, each of who contributed enormously to making the observatories what they are today. Ron Probst passed away on 05 December 2022, Tom Kinman on 20 March 2023, and Roger Lynds on 16 April 2023. All three spent many years working at what began as Kitt Peak National Observatory (KPNO), staying on to the transition to the National Optical Astronomy Observatory (NOAO) and later to NSF's NOIRLab. All attained emeritus status following their retirements.

Ron Probst

Ron Probst came to KPNO in 1983 to take a scientist position. He had completed his PhD at the University of Virginia: his thesis data were obtained with the IR photometers at Kitt Peak. He was deeply involved in many NOAO developments in infrared instruments and detectors at a time when two-dimensional infrared arrays were just arriving on the astronomical scene. Most recently, he was the Principal Investigator on two heavily used infrared imagers: ISPI on the Víctor M. Blanco 4-meter Telescope in Chile and NEWFIRM on the Nicholas U. Mayall 4-meter Telescope at KPNO. NEWFIRM was so popular that it is the only instrument to have been moved from the Mayall to the Blanco, then back to the Mayall, then (after the DESI installation) back again to the Blanco to satisfy user demand. NEWFIRM on 11 January 2023 achieved “first light for the second time” on the Blanco.

One of Ron's significant but often unrecognized contributions to NOAO was promoting, implementing, and supporting significant collaborative efforts between the Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory (CTIO) and KPNO. Many staff members (not just scientists) owe Ron a debt of gratitude for drawing them into rewarding and productive collaborations with their colleagues from the Southern Hemisphere. Ron was committed to science education. He helped design an astronomy course for schoolchildren in Chile and supported public events while he lived there. A memorable event was the transit of Mercury across the disk of the sun in the late 1990s when Ron set up telescopes and spoke to students and the public about the transit at the University of La Serena. In Tucson, Ron was an active member of the Tucson Amateur Astronomy Association.

Ron Probst, 2009. Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/K. Garmany

Tom Kinman

Tom Kinman came to KPNO in 1969, having completed his PhD at the University of Oxford in 1953. He was a towering figure in the early studies of the diffuse halo of stars that surround our Galaxy: illuminating the nature of and distribution of globular clusters in the Milky Way halo and conducting one of the earliest systematic searches for RR Lyrae stars in the Milky Way halo. To analyze periods and light curves, he invented the so-called Lafler-Kinman algorithm, a simple but effective form of the “period dispersion minimization” class of methods, which remains in use to this day, with over 700 citations in ADS. During the 1960s and onwards, Kinman also became interested in the study of quasi-stellar objects (QSOs), with a focus on their variability and on polarimetry. He continued his exploration of the Galactic halo using blue horizontal branch and other A and F stars, in addition to the RR Lyraes. His studies included exploring the extended structure of the Large Magellanic Cloud (LMC) and studying long period variables in M33. He was a mentor to many students and postdocs — especially those who passed through KPNO. After retirement, Tom was ordained a Deacon at St. Michael’s and All Angels Episcopal Church in Tucson, and he took great pleasure in serving as a hospital chaplain at the University Medical Center in Tucson.

Tom Kinman in his office in 2004. *Credit: J. Kinman*

Roger Lynds

Roger Lynds received his PhD from the University of California, Berkeley, in 1955 and joined the staff of KPNO in 1961. Roger's primary interest was in optical astronomy and the development of detectors to be used on optical telescopes. Working with his friend Bill Livingston (an astronomer with the National Solar Observatory), Lynds published several papers on their experiments with electronic image intensifiers. The development of such systems allowed the [KPNO 2.1-meter Telescope](#) at Kitt Peak to compete on equal terms with larger telescopes using traditional photographic detectors. Notably, Roger used spectra obtained with the 2.1-meter to discover what he [described](#) as "the Lyman-alpha forest" in the far UV spectra of QSOs, which is a dense ensemble of hydrogen lines generated by gas between us and the QSOs. Studies of the Lyman-alpha forest have subsequently emerged as a critical tool for understanding the formation and evolution of galaxies over cosmological history. In 1974 Roger was accepted as a member of the National Academy of Sciences. Also in 1974, Roger used the technique of speckle interferometry on the then-new Mayall telescope to obtain the first image of the surface of Betelgeuse, the first time anyone obtained resolved images of another star besides our Sun. When plans were being made for the *Hubble Space Telescope* (*HST*), Jim Westphal (a professor of planetary astronomy at Caltech) invited Roger to join his team in developing and using the Wide Field and Planetary Camera (WFPC), which was designed to be *HST*'s primary camera. Roger had a special interest in "strange objects" in the Universe, which defined a portion of the WFPC team's scientific investigation. As a footnote to history, shortly after the launch of *HST* in 1990, Roger was the first to

Roger Lynds lying on the floor of the Cassegrain cage at the Kitt Peak Nicholas U. Mayall 4-meter Telescope (1975). *Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA*

recognize that the *Hubble* primary mirror suffered from spherical aberration (although his assessment wasn't accepted at first). In 1989 he and Vahe Petrosian [published](#) the discovery that the mysterious arcs seen in clusters of galaxies were really background galaxies lensed by the clusters. As with his discovery of the Lyman-alpha forest, this has turned into a vital tool for understanding the Universe over all.

The entire NOIRLab staff is honored to have worked with each of these remarkable individuals during careers that spanned the history of the observatory.